

1. A conceptual model of factors influencing farmers' management of diversity (from Bellon et al 1995).

2. Factors influencing the genetic polymorphism of a land race (L_1) leading to a second land race (L_2). Farmers may also decide to create a distinct land race (L_3) (from Pham et al 1995).

One of the roles of on-farm conservation research is to test new strategies. These involve farmers managing a sample of genetic diversity in addition to their own varieties. Three ways to complement "classical" on-farm conservation are reintroducing varieties, introducing alien

varieties, and introducing composite populations. We will test the feasibility of these new strategies in developing the necessary links between ex situ and in situ conservation of rice genetic resources (Bellon et al 1995).

Cited references

- Bellon MR, J-L Pham, MT Jackson. 1995. Genetic conservation: a role for rice farmers. In: Maxted N, Ford-Lloyd BV, Hawkes JG, editors. Plant conservation: the in situ approach. London: Chapman & Hall. (in press)
- Pham J-L, Bellon MR, Jackson MT. 1995. What is on-farm conservation research on rice genetic resources? Paper presented at the Third Southeast Asia Symposium on Genetic Resources, 22-24 Aug 1995, Serpong-Jakarta, Indonesia. (in press). ■

Genetics

Genetics of the new plant type

A. P. Bentota, D. Senadhira, IRRI; M. J. Lawrence, Wolfson Laboratory for Plant Molecular Biology, School of Biological Sciences, University of Birmingham, Birmingham B15 2TT, United Kingdom

The genetical architecture of 12 quantitative characters of interest to rice breeders has been investigated in two crosses, Jinnibyeo/Gaok (cross 1) and Sangnambatbyeo/Kemandi Pance (cross 2), chosen at random from among those made in IRRI's new plant type program. Individuals of the basic generations (P_1, P_2, F_1, F_2, B_1 and B_2), F_3 , and triple test cross families ($F_2 \times P_1, F_2 \times P_2$, and $F_2 \times F_1$) were raised in a single, completely randomized block, one for each cross. Each block also contained plants of IR72 and IR74 as checks.

The parents of these crosses differed significantly for most characters, except for the proportion of filled spikelets and grain yield in cross 1 and 100-grain weight in cross 2. While three characters—panicle number, grain yield, and dry matter—displayed heterosis in the first cross, none did in the second. All of the characters in both crosses were heritable. Their heritabilities ranged from 0.65 for panicle length to 0.04 for harvest index in cross 1, and from 0.77 for dry matter to 0.14 for 100-grain weight in cross 2. The genetical architecture of the characters in cross 1 was of the relatively simple type in which the genes involved displayed either additive effects only or additive and dominance

effects. The only exception was for those determining the related characters of tiller and panicle number, which also displayed some epistasis of the additive $\times$ dominance type. On the other hand, the genetical architecture of the characters in cross 2 was more complex. With the exception of days to maturity and tiller number, all were controlled by genes that, in addition to displaying additive and dominance effects, also displayed epistatic effects, predominantly of the duplicate type.

Predictions of the proportion of recombinant inbred lines, the means of which meet the desired new plant type targets, can be extracted by single seed

descent from these crosses. Based on information obtained from F_3 families, this should be easy to achieve in both crosses for days to heading, days to maturity, tiller number, culm length, and panicle number. It will be less easy to achieve for spikelet number, doubtful to achieve for proportion of filled spikelets and harvest index, and very unlikely for grain yield in either cross.

The pattern of genetic correlations between characters, in cross 1 estimated from F_3 data, was very different from that in cross 2. Thus, while in cross 1 grain yield was moderately correlated ($r=0.56$) only to days to heading, in cross 2 it was highly correlated ($r=0.75$) to dry matter, tiller and

panicle number, panicle length, and spikelet number. This indicates that the chief cause of these correlations is the linkage disequilibrium of linked genes, rather than pleiotropy. This, in turn, suggests that it should be possible to extract inbred lines from appropriate crosses achieving the desired multiple new plant type.

Results suggest, however, that the targets for proportion of filled spikelets, for harvest index and, in particular, for grain yield will be achieved only after several cycles of inbreeding, each of which is initiated by crossing the best inbred lines from the previous cycle. ■

Molecular basis of heterosis in hybrid rice and hybrid maize revealed by mRNA amplification

Jinshui Yang, Ninghui Chen, Yanping Gao, Minlian Xu, Koulin Ge, and C. C. Tan, Institute of Genetics, Fudan University, Shanghai 200433, China

We have detected the mRNA subpopulations derived from hybrid rice, hybrid maize, and their parental lines by differential display. Messenger RNA amplification reveals that profound alteration of gene expression occurs in the hybrid genetic background when compared with parental lines. Regulation of gene expression in the hybrid environment includes enhancement, selective transcription, silencing, cosuppression, and activity of specific genes that are silencing in parental lines. Comparing gene expression patterns in hybrids with those in parental lines provides the underlying information to analyze the biological processes controlling heterosis formation.

To investigate the relationship between gene expression regulation and heterosis, we tried to use a differential display method to detect gene products from hybrid rice, hybrid maize, and their parental lines. Rice F_1 hybrids were from a cross between

two indica lines, Zhangsha 97 and Minfei 63, and maize F_1 hybrids were from a cross between two inbred cultivars, YD4 and H24. The total mRNAs of the leaves of seedlings of hybrid rice, hybrid maize, and their parental lines were isolated using the method of Liang (1993). Two anchored oligo-dT primers, 3'-T11CA and 3-T11GC, were used to reverse-transcribe the mRNA subpopulation. Two short arbitrary primers, 5-L1(5'-GATCGCATTG-3') and 5'-L2(5'-TACAACGAGG-3'), were designed to make paired primer sets and to amplify cDNA subpopulations. Amplified labeling cDNAs were separated on sequencing gel. In side-by-side comparison, significant changes of the mRNA constitution and quantity appeared in hybrid rice and hybrid maize.

Six kinds of gene expression alteration in the hybrids were detected based on amplified cDNA patterns: some new mRNAs that are absent in paternal lines appear in hybrid seedlings, meaning these genes are transcribed only in hybrids; maternal genes become inactive in hybrids; paternal genes are silencing in hybrids; allelic genes of two parental lines show cosuppression in hybrids; some genes are overexpressed in hybrids when compared with their expression in parental lines; and some genes are underexpressed in hybrids. We also found many genes expressed

normally in hybrids. We therefore conclude that in the hybrid genetic background, gene expression is altered in a variety of ways.

It was reported recently that the major genetic basis of heterosis in rice is dominance as revealed by QTL analysis using molecular markers. In contrast, it seems that the prominent factors contributing heterosis in maize is overdominance (Stuber et al 1992, Xiao et al 1995). Further studies of gene expression alternation in hybrids will provide important information about the molecular basis of overdominance and dominance in heterosis.

Cited references

- Allard RW. 1960. Inbreeding depression and heterosis. In: Principles of plant breeding. New York: John Wiley & Sons. p 213-223.
- Liag P, Averboukh L, Pardee AB. 1993. Distribution and cloning of eukaryotic mRNAs by means of differential display: refinements and optimization. *Nucleic Acids Res.* 21:3269-3275.
- Stuber et al. 1992 Identification of genetic factors contributing to heterosis in hybrid from two elite maize inbred lines using molecular markers. *Genetics* 132:823-839.
- Xiao J et al. 1995. Dominance is the major genetic basis of heterosis in rice as revealed by QTL analysis using molecular markers. *Genetics* 140:745-754. ■